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CLUSTERING ORGANIZATION DIRECTIONS BASED ON INTERNATIONAL EXPERIENCES

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Abstract: The article analyzed the state of cluster development in foreign countries and the ongoing reforms. The participation and role of the state in developing clusters in economically developed countries were revealed.

Keywords: National Economy, World Economy, Cluster, Innovation, Competitiveness, Entrepreneurship, Scientific Research, Education.

I. INTRODUCTION

In the Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On the Development Strategy of New Uzbekistan for 2022-2026" of January 28, 2022, PF-160 "Development of 464 thousand hectares of new and disused land and allocating it to clusters based on open competition. The task of growing exportable products and developing fruit and vegetable farming, increasing the area of intensive gardens by 3 times and greenhouses by 2 times, increasing the export potential to 1 billion US dollars. Today, there are 5,500 hectares of unused orchards and 2,500 hectares of vineyards, as well as several ineffective greenhouses.

To ensure the fulfillment of this task, using innovative methods of development and management to increase the competitiveness of the national economy, attention is paid to the cluster approach of economic development, which is widely used in the developed countries of the world [1]. However, not enough systematic scientific research has been conducted on the theoretical and methodological foundations of the cluster approach and its practical application.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

The following scholars have considered clustering organization directions based on international experiences in their research: Ortik E., Khurshida K., Askar

D. [4], Porter M. [6], Abdullaev A.A. [7], Rakhimov Z.G. [8], Morzhakova K.E., Kryukova O.G. [10].

III. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The methodological basis of the research was formed as a result of the study of theoretical and practical information, legislation and other legal documents, literary sources and publications. The research is based on the connections between theory and practice but also extensively uses methods such as analysis, comparison, and synthesis.

IV. ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

In the economic dictionary, the word "cluster" is derived from the English word "cluster", which means a group, or association of different things or people. A cluster (eng. cluster — accumulation, brush, swarm) is a common aspiration of several enterprises or entrepreneurs in the same area for a creative solution."[2]

According to the legal documents of some countries, "A cluster in the economy is primarily understood as an association of various subjects that are geographically close and functionally interrelated, that is, organizations, production and service enterprises, scientific research and educational institutions." There is an opinion that [3]

Michael Porter, who was the first to introduce the concept of the business cluster to science, said, "The cluster approach to economic development is a new management technology, and this approach provides an opportunity to increase the competitiveness of not only a particular region or industry, but also the entire country. According to M. Porter's theory, a cluster is a competing group. Still, at the same time cooperating, geographically concentrated, interconnected companies, specialized suppliers, service organizations (for example, universities, standardization agencies, as well as trade associations) is a united group. In his opinion, the relative advantage in the modern global economy is not in the direction

of investment funds for heavy production, but in the development of science and education, which allows constant renewal of innovations." [4]

According to A.A.Abdullaev, "The cluster approach is primarily a new management technology that increases the competitiveness of individual regions, industries or countries." [5]

Z.G. Rakhimov stated, "Clusters are groups of interrelated companies, including raw materials, components, products, services and their suppliers and communication organizations, gathered in the region." [6]

Despite the existence of different opinions and approaches to the cluster concept, clusters are used in foreign countries to increase the competitiveness of the national economy.

Figure 1

The number of clusters in some economically developed countries

Suppose we pay attention to the experience of developed foreign countries on introducing clusters. In that case, the weight of the Finnish economy, which has 0.5% of forest resources, 10% of the world's export of processed wood products and 25% of paper products, corresponds to the weight of the economy. [7]

In the US, 60 percent of GDP is generated by enterprises involved in clusters. 38 percent of the labor force of EU countries works in clusters. The economies of Norway, Sweden and Denmark are almost completely covered by clusters. [8]

He determined that 100 billion US dollars will be allocated for developing regional innovation clusters and business incubators from the 2010 budget in the USA as one factor determining the national economy's future competitiveness.

Canada has accumulated rich experience in organizing, supporting and developing clusters. Including the established and well-known biotechnology cluster (Montreal, Toronto, Vancouver, Ottawa, Halifax), and the information technology cluster (Montreal, Ontario); Examples include the wine cluster (Niagara), the food cluster (Toronto), and other clusters.

in Germany, the biotechnology cluster is the highly efficient automotive cluster in Baden-Württemberg, the medical equipment cluster in Tuttlingen, and the chip manufacturing cluster in Dresden and Berlin-Brandenburg.

Within the framework of the "Foremost" project of the "Minalogic" cluster based on micro and nanotechnology in France, relations have been established with 24 partners from 8 countries to create high-end microchips

V. CONCLUSION/RECOMMENDATIONS

In this regard, certain works are being carried out in Uzbekistan. According to the order of the head of our state, based on the "national machine-building cluster" program, the machine-building network includes 8 machine-building enterprises, more than 300 enterprises producing components, logistics, trade in domestic and foreign markets, covering the chain "engineering components - finished products - trade and service". and the service network will be developed by the method of industrial cluster. This system's scientific and innovative activities are coordinated by Turin Polytechnic and Andijan Mechanical Engineering Institutes.

Also, 100 billion soums will be allocated from the budget, and it has been decided to create a cluster by moving the equipment of the "Technolog" and "Agregat" factories to Chirchik. This cluster, which will be fully operational from 2023, will allow to double the production of agricultural machinery, reduce their cost by 12% and increase the export volume to 15 million dollars [9].

As a result of 15 business entities forming a furniture production cluster in the Tashkent region, it is possible to increase the production volume up to 10 times and reduce furniture prices by 30% [10].

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